

Mechatronics Instrumentation for Magnetic Actuation of Micro/Milli-Robots

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1 Introduction

In recent years, microscale engineering and miniaturization have been gaining importance, and advancements in these fields have created a wide range of research areas attracting the interest of researchers. Controllable particles with dimensions in the order of micrometers and millimeters named as Micro/Milli-Robots (MMRs) are one of these significant research areas. Thanks to their advantages such as small size and the ability to be manipulated untethered, MMRs can be used for various tasks in fields like targeted drug delivery, precise surgery, and lab-on-a-chip systems[1]. MMRs manipulation can be achieved through different methods, including magnetic, electrical, acoustic, optical, and chemical techniques[2]. Among these, magnetic actuators are frequently preferred due to advantages such as their ability of precise and fast manipulation and applicability in biological applications [3].

As in vitro and in-vivo applications, MMRs may need to operate in microfluidic applications that involve continuous flow. Therefore, the investigation of MMRs dynamics under a time-varying flow is gaining importance. Demircali et al. [4] analytically and experimentally investigated the longitudinal motion of a microrobot under laminar flow conditions. They have used two permanent magnets under and above the channel and vertical magnet positions are controlled by the motors. The robot which is also permanent magnet has dimensions of $\text{Ø}250 \times 250 \mu\text{m}$. Moreover, microfluidic channel has a square-shaped cross section with the dimensions of $900 \times 900 \mu\text{m}$. They have used a syringe pump to provide continuous flow, and a laser displacement sensor and a camera coupled optical microscope were used to determine the position of the microrobot. The study results show that the microrobot was successfully actuated in a linear direction at a flow rate of 4.5 mL/min. The proposed method demonstrated the ability to control the microrobot under laminar flow conditions. The study by Doğanay [5] aimed to model and control the position of MMRs under laminar flow conditions. Moreover, conceptual design of Lagrange point-based manipulation of MMRs is proposed. The study establishes an analytical model for the permanent magnet and subsequently uses an adaptive mathematical model to comprehensively analyze the MMRs' positional dynamics, considering the influence of permanent magnet diameter, channel dimensions, and the Reynolds (Re) number. The results show that the proposed adaptive model successfully enables MMRs positioning using a Lagrange point-based manipulation strategy. The use of micro/milli robots in-vivo and in-vitro applications is becoming increasingly widespread, and considering in-vivo conditions, the ability to manipulate and control MMRs in high-viscosity fluids and under-flow conditions has become critically important. Researchers have proposed various types of actuators and manipulation methods. However, manipulation of MMRs under laminar flow using a Lagrange point-based magnetic actuation strategy has not yet been experimentally investigated in the literature. Herein, a mechatronic system design is presented for proof-of-concept experiments.

2 Mechatronics System Design for Magnetic Actuation of MMR

Lagrange point-based manipulation is considered an effective method for achieving accurate positioning of magnetic objects when utilizing magnetic actuators [5]. Shapiro et al. [6] pioneered a novel magnetic system, demonstrating that by arranging two permanent magnets, they could generate a local minimum magnetic field. This minimum field creates a Lagrange point, which successfully enables the precise manipulation of magnetic particles. The actuation concept relies on placing two identical cylindrical permanent magnets with the same poles facing each other, symmetrically tilted by an angle θ (Figure 1a). While a single magnet's field is unique at every point, coupling two identical magnets creates two magnetic field vectors of equal magnitude but opposite directions. This precise configuration causes the magnetic fields to cancel each other out at a specific distance from the center, resulting in a zero magnetic field area known as the Lagrange point (LP). The magnetic gradients generated by the permanent magnets generates a motive force on the MMR Equation 1:

$$\mathbf{F}_m = V(\mathbf{M} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{B} \quad 1$$

Where V represents the magnetizable volume of MMR, \mathbf{M} is the magnetization vector, and \mathbf{B} is the magnetic flux density. When an MMR is released into the fluid in a microfluidic system equipped with a magnetic actuator, it is subjected to magnetic force, drag force, lift force, van der Waals force, contact forces, and electrostatic interaction forces. Van der Waals and electrostatic interaction forces are considered negligible in comparison to the dominant forces acting on the system (Figure 1b), due to their relatively small magnitudes under the operating conditions and we simply get Equation 2 [7]:

$$m \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_m + \mathbf{F}_d \quad 2$$

where \mathbf{F}_d represents drag force on the MMR and can be calculated by using Equation 3 for microsphere MMR:

$$\mathbf{F}_d \approx -6\pi\eta_f r(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}_f)$$

where η_f is the fluid viscosity, r is the radius of the microsphere, \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{v}_f represent velocity of the MMR and fluid velocity respectively.

Figure 1. (a) Lagrange point-based actuation strategy, (b) forces acting on MMR

Figure 2 shows the block diagram of the proposed mechatronic system. A syringe pump will be designed to provide steady or pulsatile flow for in-vivo applications within a microchannel. A Lagrange point-based PMA will be designed to control and manipulate the MMR under continuous flow. The position of the Lagrange point created on the microchannel depends on parameters such as the distance and angle between the magnets. These parameters will be controllable in the PMA design. Due to the flow within the microchannel, the MMR position and velocity may change; therefore, the MMR position and velocity will be detected with a camera. Furthermore, the PMA will be integrated with a macro manipulator and will attempt to maintain the MMR at the reference position based on the data received from the camera.

Figure 2. Block diagram of proposed system

3 Conclusion

This study proposes a mechatronic system design for the manipulation and control of MMR under continuous flow. A syringe pump will provide laminar flow within the microchannel. Under continuous flow, the MMR is expected to be trapped at the Lagrange point, thus enabling its control and manipulation. Future work will involve the designing and prototyping of the syringe pump to ensure laminar flow. Moreover, PMA parameters will be determined because high magnetic forces in confined working areas can affect the precise positioning of the MMR. Finally, proof-of-concept experiments will be conducted by integrating the syringe pump, PMA, microchannel, and camera system.

References

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